

A Retrospective Study on the Correlation of Dimension of Nd: YAG Laser Posterior Capsulotomy with Visual Acuity and Refraction

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Abstract:

Purpose: The purpose of this study was to correlate the dimension of Nd: YAG laser capsulotomy with visual acuity and refraction.

Materials and Methods: This was a retrospective study. 100 eyes were included in the study. All the patients had undergone Nd: YAG laser capsulotomy for Posterior Capsular Opacification between April 2022 to March 2023. The patients were divided into 4 groups based on the size and shape of capsular opening after laser. Group A) Circular opening ≤ 4 mm, Group B) Circular opening > 4 mm, Group C) Cruciate opening ≤ 4 mm, Group D) Cruciate opening > 4 mm.

Results: 100 eyes had pearl type of P.C.O. The mean age at presentation was 58.5 years with standard deviation of 6.8 years. Group D required highest laser energy (mean 1.8 millijoule) while in Group A least laser firing was needed (mean 1.1 millijoule). Post laser the vision improved but there was no statistically significant changes in refraction and spherical equivalent amongst the 4 groups ($p = 0.9$) Intra ocular pressure was within normal limits post laser.

Conclusion: The size and shape of laser capsulotomy opening doesn't affect the refractive outcome although bigger opening may result in complications due to increased laser firing.

Keywords: Posterior capsular opacification, Nd: YAG laser.

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Introduction

Posterior capsular opacification, also known as after cataract is the most common late complication following cataract surgery. One study noted that the incidence of posterior capsular opacification (PCO) was 28.4% after 5 years of cataract surgery. [1] The pathogenesis of PCO mainly involves the epithelium cells in the equatorial lens bow which actively divide and migrate towards the posterior capsule resulting in PCO. [2] PCO is profound in young individuals due to increased mitotic activity. The opacification leads to decreased visual acuity, glare and diminished contrast sensitivity.[2,3] Visual acuity is directly proportional to the severity of PCO.[4]

When the opacification is minimal, contrast sensitivity and glare disability can be affected, even though visual acuity maybe normal.[5] Various measures during cataract surgery can reduce the rate of PCO like a centered continuous curvilinear capsulorrhexis, thorough cortical cleanup, intraocu-

lar lens (IOL) placement in the bag, hydrophobic IOL etc. [6] Neodymium Yttrium Aluminum Garnet laser posterior capsulotomy is the most widely preferred choice for the treatment of PCO.[7] This is a laser procedure using photo disruption to ablate the central posterior capsule to clear the visual axis. This laser has a wavelength of 1064nm in the infrared range.[8] The two commonly used shapes to open the posterior capsule are cruciate and circular.

The size of the opening may vary from 3mm to 6mm. Larger opening runs the risk of retinal detachment, cystoid macular edema and raised intraocular pressure. [9],[10] Smaller openings may not have the desired visual recovery.

Therefore the present study attempts to evaluate the correlation of visual acuity and refraction with the size and shape of posterior capsular opening after Nd: YAG laser capsulotomy.

Materials and Methods

The present study was approved by the institutional ethical committee. Written consent was taken from all participants included in the study. The tenets of the declaration of Helsinki were strictly adhered to. This was a retrospective hospital-based study. A total of 80 patients and 100 eyes were enrolled for the study. All the patients had undergone Nd:YAG laser posterior capsulotomy for PCO between April 2022 to March 2023. The PCO had developed following cataract surgery at various time zones. All the patients had undergone phacoemulsification with foldable intraocular lens implantation by the same surgeon. The machine employed for laser was VISULAS YAG II from Zeiss, Germany. All the lasers were performed by the same surgeon. Prior to laser 0.5% proparacaine eye drop was instilled followed by one drop of Brimonidine. After the laser, Brimonidine drops were instilled to prevent post laser spike in intraocular pressure. Patients were prescribed steroid antibiotic combination eye drops in the lasered eye for one week. Prior to laser, complete evaluation of the eyes was done. Visual acuity, refraction, intraocular pressure, slit lamp biomicroscopic examination of the anterior segment and fundus examination were done. Type of PCO was noted.

Exclusion Criteria: Patients with the following conditions were excluded from the study –

- Retinal detachment

- Corneal opacity
- Ocular surface disorders
- Severe dry eyes
- Cystoid macular edema
- Any other anterior or posterior segment opacities

The lasered patients were grouped into 4 categories based on the size and shape of posterior capsular opening after laser. The sample size of each group was 25 eyes.

Group A – circular opening ≤ 4 mm

Group B – circular opening > 4 mm

Group C – cruciate opening ≤ 4 mm

Group D – cruciate opening > 4 mm

The laser settings were recorded. Post laser intraocular pressure, best corrected visual acuity, anterior segment and posterior segment findings were documented on the day of laser and also one week, one month, and 3 months post laser. Statistical analysis was done using the SPSS software. Appropriate tests like Chi Square test, Mann Whitney test, etc were utilized. A P value < 0.05 was considered statistically significant.

Results

80 patients with 100 eyes affected with PCO were included in the study. Out of 80 patients, 45 were male and 35 were female.

Table 1: Gender distribution

Sex	Number of patients	Percentage %
Male	45	56.25%
Female	35	43.75%
Total	80	100%

Unilateral PCO was recorded in 60 cases, out of which 40 were males and 20 females. Bilateral PCO was seen in 20 cases. (10 males and 10 females).

Table 2: Laterality

Gender	Unilateral	Bilateral
Male	40 (50%)	10 (12.5%)
Female	20 (25%)	10 (12.5%)
Total	60 (75%)	20 (25%)

Thus 75% of cases had unilateral PCO and 25% had bilateral PCO. Age distribution – The age range of 80 patients were between 48 to 70 years.

Table 3: Age distribution

Age	Number of patients	Percentage %
60-70	32	40%
50-59	40	50%
< 50	8	10%
Total	80	100%

The mean age at presentation was 58.5 years with a standard deviation of 6.8 years. The mean interval between surgery and Nd: YAG laser capsulotomy was 25.08 months with standard deviation of 6.09 months (9-40 months range). All cases (100 eyes) had pearl type of PCO (100%). Additional Sommering ring was seen in 15 eyes (15%). The mean laser energy applied in various groups is stated below:

Figure 1:

The mean energy used in group A was 1.1 millijoules (mj) in group B, the mean value was 1.3 millijoules (range 1.00 – 1.6mj). In group C, the mean energy was 1.6 millijoules (range 1.2 – 1.8mj) and in group D, the mean energy was 1.8 millijoules (range 1.2 – 2mj) least energy was required for group A and maximum energy was required for group D participants. The best corrected visual acuity of each group before and after laser are grouped below:

Table 4: Best corrected visual acuity

BCVA in LOGMAR units	Group A n = 25 circular ≤ 4mm	Group B n = 25 circular >4mm	Group C n = 25 cruciate ≤4mm	Group D n = 25 cruciate >4mm
Pre Laser	0.64	0.70± 0.06	0.68±0 .09	0.68 ±0.07
Post 1 week	0.20±0.1	0.10±0.1	0.20±0.1	0.20±0.1
Post 1 month	0.20±0.1	0.10±0.1	0.20±0.1	0.20±0.1
Post 3 month	0.20±0.1	0.10±0.1	0.20±0.1	0.20±0.1

The p value of post laser BCVA amongst the four groups after 1 week, 1 month and 3 months was found to be 0.9, which was statistically insignificant. There was no change in intraocular pressure after 1 week, 1 month and 3 months post laser. Spherical equivalent: The spherical equivalent of the four groups are as follows –

Table 5 : Spherical equivalent

Spherical equivalent	Group A n = 25 circular ≤4mm	Group B n = 25 circular >4mm	Group C n = 25 cruciate ≤4mm	Group D n = 25 cruciate >4mm
Pre laser	-1.75±0.50	-1.95±0.43	-1.75±0.54	-1.85±0.64
Post 1 week	-0.75±0.35	-0.70±0.18	-0.85±0.25	-0.90±0.40
Post 1 month	-0.75±0.35	-0.70±0.18	-0.85±0.25	-0.90±0.40
Post 3 month	-0.75±0.35	-0.70±0.18	-0.85±0.25	-0.90±0.40

Discussion

Nd : YAG laser capsulotomy is a common procedure performed for P.C.O. It not only improves visual acuity but also enhances contrast sensitivity and decreases glare. [11] If the size of capsulotomy opening is smaller than the scotopic pupil, it will result in glare and compromise visual acuity and contrast sensitivity.[12] On the contrary, a larger capsulotomy would require more laser energy which may lead to complications like retinal detachment [13] and posterior hyperopic shift of IOL. [14] In our study, 100 eyes with P.C.O. had undergone Nd: YAG laser capsulotomy. 62.5% of the sample were males and 37.5% were

females. 75% cases had unilateral P.C.O. and bilateral P.C.O. was seen in 25% cases.

The mean age at presentation was 58.5 years with standard deviation of 6.8 years. All the cases had pearl P.C.O. (100%). The mean interval between surgery and laser was 25.08 ±6.09 months. (range 9-40 months). Mean laser energy required for group A was lowest and highest energy was required for group D. There was no change in intraocular pressure in any groups after 1 week, 1 month, and 3 months post laser. The visual acuity and spherical equivalent improved significantly after laser in all groups but there was no change in visual acuity and spherical equivalent amongst the groups post laser (p =0.9) Our study found similar

results with a study conducted by Server Cetinkaya [15] et al. There was no complications seen in any of the cases post laser.

Conclusion

In conclusion, circular or cruciate opening doesn't affect the visual outcome after Nd: YAG laser capsulotomy. It is better to keep the size of capsulotomy opening <4mm which require less laser energy and thus less chance of complications.

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